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CARPOS

Coachable Robot for Fruit
Picking Operations

D7 - Multimodal skill encoding and generalization in fruit geometry variations

Abstract:

This deliverable reports on the multimodal skill encoding methods employed, enhanced and developed in the CARPOS project, highlighting their generalization capabilities with respect to variations of the fruit's position, orientation and size. The developed encoding mechanism is able to fuse data from multiple visual demonstrations towards the skill encoding and, in turn, allow the refinement of the learned skill through kinesthetic teaching. In the core of the developed method is a Dynamic Movements Primitives (DMP) model that encodes the pose of the robot (oriented trajectory), while the data fusion is achieved utilizing a variant of the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF). Furthermore, the forces applied by the fingertip are recorded and encoded using an Radial Base Function (RBF) Network. Lastly, the research activities related to this deliverable also include the investigation of employing LLMs (such as the ChatGPT) for segmenting a fruit picking motion pattern and classifying the segments into primitive actions, e.g. pull, slide, tilt etc; the related work will be presented as a poster in the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN 2025), attached at the Appendix of this deliverable. The encoding mechanism is evaluated on the CARPOS robotic system (Husky clear-path platform with a UR10e manipulator), demonstrating its adaptability and generalization capabilities in different fruit sizes and poses, as well as its ability to accumulate and encode knowledge from the human.

Περίληψη στα Ελληνικά

Αυτό το παραδοτέο καταγράφει τις μεθόδους πολυτροπικής κωδικοποίησης δεξιοτήτων που αναπτύχθηκαν στο έργο CARPOS, επισημαίνοντας τις δυνατότητες γενίκευσης σε σχέση με τις μεταβολές της θέσης, του προσανατολισμού και του μεγέθους των φρούτων. Ο μηχανισμός κωδικοποίησης που αναπτύχθηκε είναι σε θέση να συγχωνεύσει δεδομένα από πολλαπλές οπτικές επιδείξεις για την κωδικοποίηση δεξιοτήτων και, στην συνέχεια, να επιτρέψει τη βελτίωση της δεξιότητας μέσω της κιναισθητικής διδασκαλίας. Στον πυρήνα της αναπτυγμένης μεθόδου βρίσκεται ένα μοντέλο Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) που κωδικοποιεί την γενικευμένη θέση του ρομπότ (προσανατολισμένη τροχιά), ενώ η συγχώνευση επιτυγχάνεται χρησιμοποιώντας μια παραλλαγή του Εκτεταμένου Φίλτρου Kalman (EKF). Επιπλέον, οι δυνάμεις που ασκούνται από το άκρο του κύριου δακτύλου της αρπάγης καταγράφονται και κωδικοποιούνται χρησιμοποιώντας ένα δίκτυο Συναρτήσεων Ακτινικής Βάσης (RBFs). Τέλος, οι ερευνητικές δραστηριότητες που σχετίζονται με αυτό το παραδοτέο περιλαμβάνουν επίσης τη διερεύνηση της χρήσης μοντέλων LLM (όπως το ChatGPT) για την κατάτμηση ενός μοτίβου κίνησης συλλογής φρούτων και την ταξινόμηση των τμημάτων σε πρότυπες ενέργειες, π.χ. τράβηγμα, ολίσθηση, στρίψιμο κ.λπ. Η σχετική εργασία θα παρουσιαστεί ως poster στο 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN 2025), το οποίο επισυνάπτεται στο Παράρτημα αυτού του παραδοτέου. Ο μηχανισμός κωδικοποίησης αξιολογείται στο ρομποτικό σύστημα CARPOS (πλατφόρμα Clearpath Husky με ρομποτικό βραχίονα UR10e), επιδεικνύοντας την προσαρμοστικότητα και τις δυνατότητες γενίκευσης σε διαφορετικά μεγέθη και πόζες φρούτων, καθώς και την ικανότητά του να συσσωρεύει και να κωδικοποιεί γνώση από τον άνθρωπο.

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction and problem description

CARPOS project aims at developing a coachable robotic system, able to learn from human demonstrations, through multiple modalities, such as visual observations and kinesthetic teaching. It is therefore evident that the “encoding” of the skill that is captured through this process is of imperative importance. On the one hand, in order for the skill to be generalized in position, orientation and size variations¹, the skill encoding mechanism has to possess generalization capabilities, which generally could be solved by using a relatively large training dataset. On the other hand, given the involvement of the human in the training loop and the limited resources (e.g. plants) during the training procedure, the minimization of the number of demonstrations is also critical, as each demonstration involves the detachment of one fruit and requires a non-negligible time from the human-teacher. To tackle these conflicting challenges, the research team of CARPOS employed and enhanced the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) model, which is able to encode a skill even based only on a single demonstration, by providing it with multimodal learning capabilities, after taking into account the uncertainty involved in each modality.

The proposed encoding mechanism fuses the visual data using a variant of the Extended Kalman Filter for yielding the “training dataset” of the DMP model in each iteration of demonstration. As detailed in D4 (“Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception”), we consider a visual sensor (i.e. camera), attached to the robot’s end-effector, which is actively moving in order to maximize the information gain about the human demonstration. This change of perspective, from iteration to iteration, means that the uncertainty of the estimated human hand changes accordingly. The developed data fusion mechanism, reported in this deliverable, takes into account the uncertainty of the visual data at each iteration, and complementary uses the data in

¹ During the execution of the autonomous harvesting task the fruits are located in different positions and orientations, and come in different sizes.

order to optimally extract the spatial and temporal characteristics of the skill. During the last step of the training procedure, this of the inspection and kinesthetic correction, the visually trained skill is used as the basis of the motion and the human can complementary do final small modifications to the task along the directions with the higher uncertainty. This part essentially fuses the visually perceived data with some complementary ones from the kinesthetic corrections. The human-user can intervene whenever she/he deems it necessary through the application of forces (more details can be found in D5 - "Controller for unintentional and intentional pHRI during the coaching and autonomous operation").

For enabling the encoding of the forces that should be exerted by the main finger (thumb) of the gripper for a successful fruit detachment, the gripper is equipped with a force sensor that registers the forces applied towards its contact axis in real-time. To this aim, the force measurements are recorded and encoded through a Radial Base Function (RBF) interpolation, during the kinesthetic teaching.

Lastly, for providing high level semantic understanding capabilities to the system during the training procedure, we perform an initial investigation on the capabilities of LLMs, such as ChatGPT, for segmenting a complete fruit picking motion sequence into primitive patterns, such as "pushing", "twisting" etc. Our aim is to automatically extract the sequence of primitive actions that this specific fruit picking operation requires. This last investigation was not included in the initial research plan (i.e. the Technical Document), but it constitutes the first step towards the extension of the methods developed in CARPOS project for encoding a motion pattern. This investigation and its results will be presented as a Late Breaking Results (LBR) poster at the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN 2025); the related poster, as well as the corresponding technical report are provided in the Appendix of this deliverable.

1.2 Relation to Other Deliverables

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the methods developed within the CARPOS project for tackling the problem of encoding a fruit picking skill. The deliverable is closely related to D3 - "Fruit Picking Action Identification and Skill Extraction from Visual Observation" and D4 - "Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception", as the data fusion mechanism (presented here), the perception module and the control scheme for occlusion avoidance are interconnected. In particular, the purpose of the control schemes developed in D4 is to minimize the uncertainty of the pose of the human hand, which is essentially provided by the data fusion mechanism (detailed in this Deliverable), while the fusion mechanism, in turn, depends on the pose of the camera which is dictated by the aforementioned control methods. Furthermore, the deliverable is related to D5 - "Controller for unintentional and intentional pHRI during the coaching and autonomous operation", as after the multiple iterations of visual observation of the human activity, the skill is kinesthetically refined and the encoding mechanism accounts for the physically merged visual and kinesthetic data. Lastly, as the encoding mechanism detailed in this deliverable constitutes the core of the CARPOS framework, this deliverable is also related to D8 - "System integration and Testing".

METHODOLOGY

As opposed to the explicit robot programming, Learning by Demonstration (LbD) was recently proposed to provide methods that make the system able of learning intuitively and seamlessly from human actions [1, 2]. Although relieving humans from the burden of possessing technical knowledge, LbD still requires a number of human demonstrations, in the form of time-series of the pose (position and orientation) of the human hand. Such demonstrated motions are captured, in the literature, either through external means, such as cameras or magnetic trackers [3-5], or through kinesthetic teaching, i.e. by directly interacting with the robot through the exertion of contact forces [6-8].

To encode the skill, all encoding mechanisms involve a number of parameters that has to be “trained”. Towards this direction, the “learning” procedure consists essentially of finding the optimal parameters that make the system yield a behavior which is closest to the demonstrated motion, as shown in Fig. 1. However, one of the key features of such mechanism concerns the generalization of the motion in different conditions, such as new initial states, new targets or even different task orientations.

Figure 1 – Learning a demonstrated motion and generalizing in space

Due to their real-time generation and generalization (spatial and temporal) capabilities, the most dominant encoding mechanisms, in robotics literature, are the ones that employ Dynamical Systems (DS). According to DSs, the motion reference is generated in real-time based on the state of the system and the environmental condition. The most popular DSs for encoding the spatial and temporal characteristics of a motion are the Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) [9, 10] and the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) [11, 12]; one can find more details about the current DSs for encoding motion patterns in [13]. Some of the advantages of the DMPs over the GMMs is that they do not require a large training dataset, which means that the system can “learn” based only on some demonstrations (even based on a single demonstration), as well as their low computation complexity. On the other hand, although GMMs possess better generalization capabilities, their performance, in terms of encoding and generalization, depends proportionally on the number of the motion demonstrations provided as a training dataset. In our

Figure 2 – The considered {F} and {G} frames

case, in which the minimization of the required demonstrations is a crucial aspect, as the human has to perform the task in each iteration and the detachment of a fruit is involved, we selected the utilization of the DMPs for encoding the motion of the human hand during the task.

As detailed in Deliverable 3 - “Fruit Picking Action Identification and Skill Extraction from Visual Observation”, in the initial step of the visual observation of the human action, the human hand grasp pose is captured with respect to the pose of the fruit, as depicted in Fig. 2. Let $\{F\}$ and $\{G\}$ be the coordinate frame of the fruit and human-hand respectively; which are defined based on six points of interest on the fruit and human-hand, as detailed in D3. This grasp information constitutes the basis of the learned skill, and it is stored as a part of the acquired knowledge. Let $\mathbf{g}_{fh} \in SE(3)$ be the grasp pose of the human hand with respect to the fruit, in a homogeneous transformation form.

Given that the grasp pose is stored as a part of the skill knowledge, the motion of the human hand is encoded with respect to its initial pose. In this way, during the autonomous execution of the motion pattern, after ensuring that the grasping of the fruit is identical to the one performed by the human, the motion is executed with respect to the initial pose of the robot’s gripper, which in turn depends on the exact position and orientation of the fruit. This ensures that the motion will be generalized to different positions and orientations of the fruits, as depicted in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 - Two different cases involving different poses of fruit

Let $\mathbf{g}_d(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_d(t) & \mathbf{p}_d(t) \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in SE(3)$ be the pose of the human hand during the skill demonstration with respect to its initial pose, where $\mathbf{R}_d(t) \in SO(3)$, $\mathbf{p}_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the orientation (in a rotation matrix form) and position (in Cartesian coordinates) of the hand with respect to its initial pose respectively, and $t \in [0, T]$ the time, with $T \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the total duration of the motion. The goal of the encoding mechanism is, based on this demonstrated (or data fused) pattern, to find the optimal parameters of the DMP model, in order its behavior to

optimally mimic the given pattern. In the following section preliminaries about the specific DMP model variant utilized are provided.

2.1 Preliminaries on the Dynamic Movement Primitives model in $SE(3)$

For the sake of simplicity, let us first explain the encoding of a scalar variable (e.g. a single axis of the motion of the end-effector) utilizing a Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) model. Let $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ be the variable, whose behavior we want to encode and $y_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ a demonstrated trajectory or a trajectory estimate after the fusion of multiple demonstrations, where $t \in [0, T]$ with $T \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the total duration of the motion. The DMP model is a second order dynamical system of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau^2 \ddot{y} &= a(b(y_T - y) - \tau \dot{y}) + s f(x; \mathbf{w}), \\ \tau \dot{x} &= g(x),\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where $\dot{y} \triangleq \frac{dy}{dt}$, $\ddot{y} \triangleq \frac{d^2y}{dt^2}$, $y_T \in \mathbb{R}$ the final/goal value of y , i.e. $y(t) \rightarrow y_T$, $\tau, s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ the time scaling and spatial scaling parameters respectively, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ the constant parameters of the linear part of the DMP, and $x \in \mathbb{R}$ an auxiliary variable called the “phase variable” that replaces time, in order for the system to be time-independent. Notice that the dynamics of x are governed by the function $g(x): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (the so-called “canonical system”), for which there are multiple different selections in the literature; the most common ones are $g(x) \triangleq -a_x x$ (the so-called “exponential” dynamics) and $g(x) \triangleq 1$ with saturation such that $x \in [0, 1]$ (the so-called “linear” dynamics). However, the part which essentially encodes the motion pattern is the non-linear term of the DMP, which is represented by the function $f(x; \mathbf{w}): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which is called the “forcing” term, where $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ are the parameters that are adjusted in order for the behavior of the dynamic system to optimally reflect the demonstrated motion, i.e. $y_d(t)$, $\forall t \in [0, T]$, with $N \in \mathbb{N}$ being the pre-defined number of the parameters. More specifically, this non-linear term is selected to be a weighted summation of Radial Base Function (RBFs), with the most common selection for RBF being the Gaussian function. Therefore, function $f(x; \mathbf{w})$ has the following form:

$$f(x; \mathbf{w}) \triangleq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i \psi_i(x)}{\sum_{i=1}^N \psi_i(x)} = \mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}(x),\tag{2}$$

where $\mathbf{w} \triangleq [w_1 \dots w_N]^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$ the weights of the kernels (i.e. the RBFs), $\psi_i(x): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the RBF and $\boldsymbol{\Psi}(x) \triangleq [\psi_1(x) \dots \psi_N(x)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$ the kernel base (RBF base). Notice that the kernel base is constructed in the one dimensional space of the phase variable, i.e. is a function of x . The Gaussian RBF, utilized in CARPOS project, is the following:

$$\psi_i(x) \triangleq e^{-h_i(x-c_i)^2},\tag{3}$$

where $c_i, h_i \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ the centers and width of the i -th kernel. For more details on how to select these variables, one can refer to [11-13]. An example of the RBF base is provided visually in Fig. 4 for $N = 10$ and considering a linear canonical system.

Figure 4 – The kernel base for $N=10$. The RBFs appear in different colors. The phase variable is selected to be governed by linear dynamics.

For ensuring that the behavior of the DMP, as a motion generation mechanism, will optimally reflect the demonstrated motion, i.e. $y_d(t)$, one has to solve the following optimization problem:

$$\mathbf{w}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} \int_0^T (f_d(t) - f(x(t); \mathbf{w}))^2 dt, \quad (4)$$

where $f_d(t) = \dot{y}_d(t) - a(b(y_d(T) - y_d(t)) - \dot{y}_d(t))$ is the calculated “ideal” forcing term based on the demonstration, with $y_d(T) \in \mathbb{R}$ the final value of $y_d(t)$ of the demonstration, considering (for the training) that the demonstrated motion is neither scaled in time (i.e. $\tau = 1$), nor in space (i.e. $s = 1$). As the motion is captured in discrete time, e.g. with 30 fps if it is captured through a camera, the optimization problem given in (4) is written in discrete time as follows:

$$\mathbf{w}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} \sum_{k=1}^{k_T} (f_{d,k} - f(x_k; \mathbf{w}))^2. \quad (5)$$

One can yield the analytic solution of (5), using the Least Square (LS) solver, provided by:

$$\mathbf{w}^* = \tilde{\Psi}^{\mathcal{L}\dagger} \mathbf{f}_d, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\tilde{\Psi} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \Psi(x_{k=1}) \\ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \psi_i(x_{k=1})}{\vdots} \\ \Psi(x_{k=M}) \\ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \psi_i(x_{k=M})}{\vdots} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}, \quad (7)$$

with $M \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of samples within the time-series of the demonstrated motion, $\mathbf{f}_d \triangleq [f_{d,k=1} \dots f_{d,k=M}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^M$ is the array of the values of f_d at each time instance of the demonstration and $\tilde{\Psi}^\dagger \triangleq (\tilde{\Psi}^\top \tilde{\Psi})^{-1} \tilde{\Psi}^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ is the left Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of $\tilde{\Psi}$.

An example of the encoding achieved by the DMP model for a single axis is shown in Fig. 5, in which one can compare the initial demonstrated motion, with the behavior of the DMP. Notice that the encoding accuracy is improved with the increase of the number of kernel functions used (i.e. N). As Fig. 5 presents the exact value (not the derivative) of y , one can see the function approximation of $f_d(t)$ achieved by $f(x; \mathbf{w})$ after the training of the DMP in Fig. 6, which is the goal of the optimization problem of (4).

Figure 5 – Encoding of a demonstrated trajectory with a DMP, using 10 and 20 kernels

Figure 6 – Function approximation of the forcing term achieved with $N=20$ kernels. Orange line: $f(x(t))$, blue line: $f_d(t)$.

In Figures 7a and 7b, the effect of scaling the motion in space and time is shown respectively, during the execution (motion generation), after the training based on a motion demonstration.

Figure 7 – Spatial and temporal scaling of the learned behavior with the DMP model.

The data utilized for the above examples are taken from one of the joints of a 7dof KUKA LWR4+ robotic manipulator, during a physical guidance by the user.

DMP model for encoding position (DMP in \mathbb{R}^3)

As we want to encode the action of the human hand, the DMP model is extended in \mathbb{R}^3 for considering the three axes of translation, with respect to the initial frame of the hand (as explained above). In particular, let $\mathbf{p}_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the position of the human hand during the demonstration. Then the single-axis DMP model, detailed above, is extended as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau^2 \ddot{\mathbf{p}} &= a(b(\mathbf{p}_T - \mathbf{p}) - \tau \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + s \mathbf{f}_p(x; \mathbf{w}), \\ \tau \dot{x} &= g(x), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the target position and $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the position reference generated in real time by the DMP model during the autonomous execution, while similarly to (2) the forcing term is provided by:

$$\mathbf{f}_p(x; \mathbf{w}) \triangleq \mathbf{W}_p^T \Psi(x) \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{W}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 3}$ being, in this case, a matrix of the learned “weights” in order for the model’s behavior to optimally reflect the demonstrated pattern.

Notice that there is only a single phase variable for all three axes of the motion, in order for the produced motion to be synchronized. Further, notice that the same scalar parameters are utilized for both the linear part but also the spatial and temporal scaling of the skill.

The training procedure, based on the dataset provided through motion capture or data fusion of multiple demonstrations, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3, t \in [0, T]$, is done in each axis by employing (5) for each column of \mathbf{W}_p separately.

DMP model for encoding orientation (DMP in $SO(3)$)

One important characteristic of the fruit picking motions is the orientation of the human hand during the operation. For instance, for detaching a tomato of the “Elpida” variety from the branch, one should significantly rotate her/his hand, as shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8 – Motion for detaching a tomato of the Elpida variety

In the literature there are multiple DMP variants that tackle the problem of encoding the orientation of the required skill. In particular, one of the first attempts was by A. Ude et al. [14], where the quaternion logarithmic error was firstly employed for encoding the orientation. However, a newer more recent DMP variant, proposed by L. Koutras et al. [15], enhances the encoding based on the logarithm by avoiding undesired oscillatory behaviors derived when utilizing the method proposed in [14], as well as large deviations from the demonstrated motion pattern. In CARPOS project, the DMP proposed in [15] is employed, which firstly maps the orientation to the logarithmic error space (for the encoding) and, in turn, performs the inverse mapping during the execution.

Let $\mathbf{Q}_d(t) \in \mathbb{S}^3$ be the orientation of the human hand during the demonstration, in unit quaternion form, where $\mathbb{S}^n = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}: \|\mathbf{x}\| = 1\}$ is the $(n + 1)$ -th dimensional unit sphere. One can calculate $\mathbf{Q}_d(t)$ from $\mathbf{R}_d(t)$ based on the formulas provided in [16]. However, as each orientation corresponds to two (opposite) unit quaternions, i.e. $\mathbf{Q}_d(t)$ and $-\mathbf{Q}_d(t)$, one has to select between these two. In our case, in order to ensure the continuity of the demonstrated pattern, starting from $\mathbf{Q}_d(0)$, we filter the $\mathbf{Q}_d(t)$ time-series by selecting, at each time step k , the closest unit quaternion, from the two options, that is closer to the previous one, i.e. $k - 1$.

The method proposed in [15], considers the following dynamical system, i.e. orientation variant of (1):

$$\begin{aligned}\tau \dot{\mathbf{z}} &= -a_z(b_z \mathbf{e}_Q + \mathbf{z}) + s_z \mathbf{f}_z(x; \mathbf{W}_o), \\ \tau \dot{\mathbf{e}}_Q &= \mathbf{z}, \\ \tau \dot{x} &= g(x),\end{aligned}\tag{10}$$

where

$$\mathbf{e}_Q \triangleq 2 \log(\mathbf{Q}_g * \bar{\mathbf{Q}})\tag{11}$$

with $\mathbf{Q}_g \in \mathbb{S}^3$ being the goal of the trajectory, “*” denoting the quaternion product, $\bar{\mathbf{Q}} \in \mathbb{S}^3$ denoting the quaternion inverse and $\log(\cdot): \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ being the logarithmic mapping of quaternions, which yields the quantity $\mathbf{n}\theta$, with $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ the angle and axis of rotation between \mathbf{Q}_g and \mathbf{Q} . Notice that $\mathbf{Q}(t)$ is the orientation of the encoded motion while \mathbf{e}_Q is the current orientation error from the goal orientation. Further, notice that the parameters $a_z, b_z, s_z, \mathbf{W}_o$ as well as the training procedure, follow the exact same rationale detailed in the DMP for encoding the position (above).

Then, as detailed in [15], the reference orientation and angular velocity for the end-effector can be calculated in real time based on the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{Q}(t) &= \overline{\exp\left(\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{e}_Q\right)} * \mathbf{Q}_g, \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} &= 2 \text{vec}(\dot{\mathbf{Q}} * \bar{\mathbf{Q}}),\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

where $\text{vec}(\cdot): \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^3$ is the function that provides the vector part of any quaternion, $\exp(\cdot): \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^3$ is the exponential mapping to the quaternion space, and

$$\dot{\mathbf{Q}} = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{Q} * \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_g * J_{\log Q}(\mathbf{Q}_g * \bar{\mathbf{Q}}) \dot{\mathbf{e}}_Q * \mathbf{Q},\tag{13}$$

with

$$J_{\log Q}(\mathbf{Q}_g * \bar{\mathbf{Q}}) \triangleq \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \theta \mathbf{n}^\top \\ \frac{\sin \theta}{\theta} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}^\top) + \cos \theta \mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}^\top \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } \theta \neq 0 \\ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, & \text{if } \theta = 0 \end{cases}\tag{14}$$

DMP model for encoding the pose of the gripper (DMP in $SE(3)$)

For addressing the problem of encoding a motion in the full task space, i.e. the pose (position and orientation) of the end-effector, we combine the DMP models in \mathbb{R}^3 and $SO(3)$. One important detail is that a single phase variable, i.e. x , is utilized in order for the reference motion in position and orientation to be synchronized and reflect as much as possible the demonstrated skill. A diagram of the complete DMP in the $SE(3)$ (special Euclidean group), encoding both the position and orientation of the end-effector is shown in Fig. 9, while the DMP code library developed in python by the CARPOS research team is provided in the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/csrl-DMPy>.

Figure 9 – The structure of the DMP model in $SE(3)$.

An example of the encoding of a motion is $SE(3)$ for each axis separately, for position $\mathbf{p}(t) \triangleq [p_1(t) p_2(t) p_3(t)]^T$ and unit quaternion $\mathbf{Q}(t) \triangleq [Q_1(t) Q_2(t) Q_3(t) Q_4(t)]^T$ is shown in Figure 10. Let us highlight that in this specific example only $N = 5$ kernel functions are utilized in each axis of motion, which means that the size of the weight matrices \mathbf{W}_p and \mathbf{W}_o , that essentially encode

the motion pattern, are only 5×3 , requiring a close to negligible memory. However, let us also denote that the number of kernels required depend on the motion pattern, as patterns with higher frequency content could potentially require more kernels, as shown in [17].

Figure 10 – Example of the encoding capabilities of the DMP model in $SE(3)$, using $N = 5$ kernels in each axis of motion. The training (demonstrated) dataset is depicted with dashed line, while the DMP evolution is depicted with solid line.

2.2 Data fusion for training

As detailed in D4 - “Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception”, at each demonstration iteration the data gathered from the visual sensor are fused with the ones provided in the previous demonstration. Towards this direction, the LAIF method (Learning by demonstration through Active Incremental data Fusion of task observations) is developed and utilized in CARPOS project, which fuses the data from the visual sensor with the already learned skill using a Kalman-filter variant, accounting for the uncertainty at each iteration.

Figure 11 – The proposed framework (LAIF) at each repetition

In particular, let ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the measured **by the sensor** generalized position of the Point Of Interest (POI), e.g. the wrist of the human, during the i -th iteration of visual demonstrations and ${}^i\mathbf{p}^*(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the total estimate provided by the proposed method at the end of the i -th repetition. The main idea of the proposed method is: a) to incrementally (at each repetition of the task demonstration) use the previous model of the task, which is provided by modelling based on the previous estimate, and b) **fuse** the new incoming measurements with the “prediction” from the DMP model for yielding the new total estimate, and so forth. The total number of repetitions required for a reliable modelling can be assessed by the covariance of the estimate. Towards this direction, the model utilized during the $(i + 1)$ -th repetition, is based and encodes the total estimate of the previous repetitions, i.e. ${}^i\mathbf{p}^*(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for all $t \in [0, T]$. Moreover, for optimizing the point of view of the sensor, an active perception control signal is proposed that moves the sensor in order to achieve minimization of the uncertainty involved in the data fusion, which is based on both the modelling and the measurement uncertainty. The active perception control law is a part of Deliverable 4 – “Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception”. The complete framework of LAIF is conceptually depicted in Fig. 11.

We assume that ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t)$ incorporates a measurement noise/error $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, i.e. ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t) = \mathbf{p} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$. This measurement noise is considered to be a random variable having a normal probability distribution, i.e. $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_n, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$, where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \in S_{++}$ is the variance-covariance matrix of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ with respect to the inertial frame, with S_{++}^n being the set of $N \times N$ positive definite matrices. The covariance matrix is assumed to be a known function of the orientation of the sensor and the position of the POI, being characterized by the following ellipsoid surface: $\mathcal{S}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \triangleq \{\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n : \mathbf{y}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} \mathbf{y} = 1\}$.

The measurement provided by the sensor is fused with the “prediction” from the DMP model by employing a covariance weighted mean (weighted least square solution) of the data. The rationale behind this selection is to give more importance to the measurement towards the directions in which it is more reliable, as compared to the reliability of the prediction provided by the current modelling, in each iteration, and vice versa. Let $\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the prediction noise, i.e. the error between the actual position of the POI and the position prediction provided by the DMP model.

Given that the DMP model is trained based on the state estimate provided at the end of the previous repetition, it incorporates the uncertainty of this estimate. Therefore, assuming a sufficiently accurate encoding, $\omega(t)$ is considered to be a random variable, having a normal distribution with covariance ${}^i\mathbf{Q}(t) \in S_{++}^m$, with $m \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of states of the DMP, which is equal to the uncertainty of the total estimate after at end of the $i - 1$ repetition (i.e. the previous total estimate), or in other words, we set:

$${}^i\mathbf{Q}(t) = {}^{i-1}\mathbf{P}(t), \forall t \in [0, T], \quad (14)$$

where ${}^{i-1}\mathbf{P}(t) \in S_{++}^m$ the covariance of the uncertainty of the total estimate during the $(i - 1)$ -th repetition, the calculation of which follows.

Remark 1. Notice that for $i = 1$, i.e. during the first repetition, there is no previous demonstrations and therefore one can consider only the linear part of the DMP with a relatively high uncertainty, e.g. ${}^i\mathbf{Q}(t) = \sigma_0^2 \mathbf{I}_m$, with $\sigma_0 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being a relatively large value. ■

For fusing the position measurement provided by the sensor, i.e. ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t)$, with the position prediction provided by the DMP model, which is denoted in this section by $\mathbf{p}_{ds}(t)$, we propose the following covariance weighted mean, as a data fusion mechanism:

$${}^i\mathbf{p}^*(t) = \left({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t) + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}(t) \right)^{-1} \left({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t)\mathbf{p}_{ds}(t) + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}(t) {}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t) \right). \quad (15)$$

Notice that (15) is essentially the weighted left pseudoinverse solution (weighted least squares) of the following forward relationship:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{ds}(t) \\ {}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_n \\ \mathbf{I}_n \end{bmatrix} {}^i\mathbf{p}^*(t), \quad (16)$$

considering the following weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_{WLS} = \text{diag} \left({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t), \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}(t) \right)$, in order to account more for the directions with less uncertainty. The variance-covariance matrix of the total estimate, i.e. ${}^i\mathbf{P}(t) \in S_{++}^m$, can then be calculated by:

$${}^i\mathbf{P}(t) = \left({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}(t) + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}(t) \right)^{-1}. \quad (17)$$

Proof of (17): Given that $\mathbf{p}_{ds}(t)$ is characterized by the modelling uncertainty, having a covariance of ${}^i\mathbf{Q}(t)$, and ${}^i\hat{\mathbf{p}}^\top(t)$ by the measurement covariance, i.e. $\mathbf{\Sigma}(t)$ and by taking into account (15), one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^i\mathbf{P}(t) &= \text{var}({}^i\mathbf{p}^*) = \\ &({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1})^{-1} {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} {}^i\mathbf{Q} {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1})^{-1} + \\ &({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1})^{-1} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1})^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Due to the fact that both ${}^i\mathbf{Q}$ and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ are symmetric positive definite matrices, we have ${}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} = {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1}$, $\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} = \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}$, $({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1})^{-1} = ({}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1})^{-1}$ and therefore, (17) yields from (18). ■

Lemma 1. An ellipsoid $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{A})$ is enclosed (or radially surrounded) by another ellipsoid $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{B})$, where $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \in \mathcal{S}_{++}^n$, if $\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{y} > \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{y}$ for all $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Proof of Lemma 1: Let $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be a unit vector pointing towards an arbitrary direction. We can show that $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{A})$ is enclosed by $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{B})$, by showing that $a < b$, where $a \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$: $(a\mathbf{k})^\top \mathbf{A} (a\mathbf{k}) = a^2 \mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{k} = 1$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$: $(b\mathbf{k})^\top \mathbf{B} (b\mathbf{k}) = b^2 \mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{k} = 1$, for any direction $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^n$: $\|\mathbf{k}\| = 1$. Notice that a and b represent the length of the linear segments within $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{A})$ and $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{B})$ respectively, along the direction of \mathbf{k} . To this aim, we have $\mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{k} = \frac{1}{a^2}$ and $\mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{k} = \frac{1}{b^2}$. Then $\mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{k} > \mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{k}$ implies $\frac{1}{a^2} > \frac{1}{b^2}$ and consequently $a < b$. ■

Theorem 1. The covariance ellipsoid of the total estimate at the i -th repetition, i.e. $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{P}(t))$, is enclosed (i.e. radially surrounded):

1. By the covariance ellipsoid of the $(i-1)$ -th repetition, i.e. $\mathcal{S}({}^{i-1}\mathbf{P})$. In other words, the uncertainty of the estimate at each repetition **will always be less than the uncertainty at the previous repetition**, along any direction.
2. By both the covariance ellipsoid of the modelling error, i.e. $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{Q})$, and the covariance ellipsoid of the measurement, i.e. $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{\Sigma})$. In other words, the uncertainty of the total estimate **will always be less than both the measurement and the modelling uncertainty**, along any direction.

Proof of Theorem 1: Given that ${}^{i-1}\mathbf{P}(t) = {}^i\mathbf{Q}(t)$ from (14), $\mathcal{S}({}^{i-1}\mathbf{P})$ will constitute the surface for which:

$$\mathbf{y}^\top ({}^{i-1}\mathbf{P})^{-1} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}^\top {}^i\mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{y} = 1, \quad \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad (19)$$

while $\mathcal{S}({}^i\mathbf{P})$ will constitute the surface for which:

$$\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}^\top (\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}) \mathbf{y} = 1, \quad \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n. \quad (20)$$

Given that both \mathbf{Q} and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ are positive definite matrices, the following will hold:

$$\mathbf{y}^\top (\mathbf{Q}^{-1} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}) \mathbf{y} > \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{y}. \quad (21)$$

After substituting (19) and (20) into (21), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{y} &> \mathbf{y}^{\top(i-1)} \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{y}, \\ \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{y} &> \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1} \mathbf{y}, \\ \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{y} &> \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{y}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

for all $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Therefore, according to **Lemma 1**, the first inequality of (22) proves the first part of **Theorem 1**, while the second and third inequalities prove the second part of it. ■

Remark 2. Assuming that one can rotate the covariance ellipsoid of the measurement, i.e. $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{\Sigma})$, by rotating the sensor, the second part of **Theorem 1** implies that the uncertainty can be optimally minimized by ensuring that $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{\Sigma})$ is orthogonal to $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{Q})$, i.e., the major axis of $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is aligned to the minor axis of \mathbf{Q} and vice versa (given that they belong to S_{++}^n). This optimization rationale is the core of the active perception controllers developed in the project, provided in Deliverable 4 – “Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception”. ■

2.3 Generalization to different fruit sizes

The generalization to different fruit geometries essentially involves the scaling of the motion given the different a) **position**, b) **orientation** and c) **size** of the fruit. As mentioned above, the DMP is encoded considering the initial pose at the exact time of grasping as the reference frame. This ensures that, when the grasping pose is exactly the same with that demonstrated, the whole motion will be performed with respect to this orientation, as depicted in Fig. 3. Therefore, this selection tackles the problem of generalizing the motion, given the different position and orientation of each fruit during the execution of the pattern.

For addressing the scaling of the motion based on the size of the fruit, we exploit a metric for the size provided by the perception module, developed in CARPOS project, as detailed in Deliverable 3 – “Fruit Picking Action Identification and Skill Extraction from Visual Observation”, e.g. the radius of the fruit. Let $r_d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ be this size measure during the human demonstration, and $r \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ be the one during the autonomous execution of the fruit picking activity. Then, the scaling term and the goal of the position part of the DMP, i.e. equation (8) above, is selected to be the following respectively:

$$s = \frac{r}{r_d}, \quad \mathbf{p}_T = \frac{r}{r_d} \mathbf{p}_f, \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_f \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the final position of the wrist with respect to the initial frame of the wrist, during the demonstration. Notice that the orientation part of the DMP is not scaled, as we assume that required rotation for the detachment of the fruit from the branch does not depend on the size of it, but mostly on the task itself.

2.4 Combining kinesthetic teaching with visual demonstrations

As explained in the Introduction, after a number of visual demonstrations, the robot attempts to execute a fruit picking procedure autonomously. However, this first attempt constitutes a preliminary phase before the actual autonomous execution, in which the inspection and correction take place, with the human being able to intervene by applying forces for correcting the parts of the motion that needs small modifications. To this aim, in CARPOS project we developed a control scheme that exploits the uncertainty of the visual observation, i.e. ${}^{\mu}\mathbf{P}(t) \in S_{++}^n$, with $\mu \in \mathbb{N}$ being the total (final) number of iterations of visual demonstrations.

In particular, the proposed LbD method, which is presented in detail in Deliverable 5 – “Controller for unintentional and intentional pHRI during the coaching and autonomous operation”, combines the advantages of both visual and kinesthetic teaching, exploiting the intuitiveness and effortlessness of learning through observation (detailed above) while benefiting from the accuracy of kinesthetic teaching. This deliverable focuses only on the **physical fusion** part of the visual data with the ones gathered through the kinesthetic teaching. The CARPOS approach leverages visual data from the visual demonstrations, captured by the in-hand camera, to assist the human-teacher in kinesthetic task instruction. Let us highlight that the proposed method does not rely on knowledge of the camera’s location relative to an inertial frame.

As also detailed in Deliverable 5, in this stage, to provide the system with compliant characteristics, we employ the notion of admittance control. Therefore, a target impedance model in the task-space of the robot is defined for the robot’s end-effector, as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} \dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_v + \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\delta}_v + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{e} = \mathbf{F}_x, \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K} \in S_{++}^6$ are the target 6D task-space positive definite inertia, damping and stiffness matrices respectively, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_v \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represents the desired deviation from the reference velocity induced by the admittance model, while $\mathbf{F}_x = [\mathbf{f}_x^T \boldsymbol{\tau}_x^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the generalized force measurement at the end-effector with $\mathbf{f}_x, \boldsymbol{\tau}_x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the force and torque applied by the user to the end-effector. Moreover,

$$\mathbf{e} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_a - \mathbf{p} \\ \log(\mathbf{Q}_a * \mathbf{Q}^{-1}) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (25)$$

is the error between the robot's pose, denoted with $\mathbf{p}_a, \mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the actual position of end-effector of the robot and the one generated in real time by the DMP model respectively, while $\mathbf{Q}_a, \mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are the actual orientation of the end-effector of the robot and the one generated by the DMP model respectively. Here, $\log(\cdot): \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ is the quaternion logarithmic mapping, "*" represents the quaternion product, and $\mathbf{Q}^{-1} \in \mathbb{S}^3$ the quaternion inverse of \mathbf{Q} (more details on quaternion algebra can be found in [22]).

For rendering these specific compliant characteristics, the commanded joint velocities are computed by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger \left(\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} - \boldsymbol{\delta}_v \right) \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^\xi$ are the joint variables and $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times \xi}$ the Jacobian matrix of the robot, with ξ being the number of joints and " \dagger " symbolizing any pseudo inverse matrix; for the CARPOS project $\xi = 8$, involving the degrees of freedom of the platform, as well as those of the robotic manipulator.

Based on (24), the selection of the impedance model parameters plays a crucial role on the directions in which the user is guided during the interaction with the robot. Specifically, the reactive force experienced by the user along a specific direction is proportional to the values of the corresponding elements of matrices \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{K} . Our aim is to append low impedance along the directions with high uncertainty.

As described above, the hand pose motion (encoded by the DMP) includes a measurement error, which is considered to be a random variable having an uncertainty characterized by ${}^\mu\mathbf{P}$. Given this uncertainty, we propose the utilization of the following anisotropic stiffness matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq \text{diag} \left(\frac{k_p}{\lambda_{pM}} \mathbf{I}_3, \frac{k_o}{\lambda_{oM}} \mathbf{I}_3 \right) {}^\mu\mathbf{P}^{-1}, \quad (27)$$

where $\lambda_{pM}, \lambda_{oM} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ denote the maximum eigenvalues of the position and orientation part of ${}^\mu\mathbf{P}$ respectively, while $k_p, k_o \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ represent the selected stiffness value on the major axis of \mathbf{K} for position and orientation, respectively. At the end of the kinesthetic correction stage, the recorded refined motion of the end-effector, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_a(t), \mathbf{Q}_a(t), \forall t \in [0, T]$, is used to retrain the DMP model.

Figure 12 – Example of the kinesthetics-enhanced skill encoding

By taking into account the non-homogeneous total uncertainty of the visually perceived data in 3D-space and guiding the user along the directions with the lowest uncertainty, the developed method essentially fuses the visually perceived data with the ones from kinesthetic teaching in the **physical (force) layer**. In particular, as the human is facilitated to do modifications towards the directions with the higher (current) uncertainty, those correction (green-shaded area in Figure 12) are incremental and complements the already known skill. Notice that if the skill is already learned with relatively low uncertainty already from the visual observations when this stage is enabled, then the human will not intentionally apply any forces and therefore the skill knowledge will remain unaltered.

Extensive experiments of this method can be found in **Deliverable 5**, in which the related paper at IEEE RO-MAN is also attached. The experimental evaluation of the current deliverable, which can be found below, involves the application of this method in the case of fruit picking.

2.5 Encoding of forces applied by the fingertip

For the encoding of the forces, a Force-Sensing Resistor (FSR) is attached to the main finger of the CARPOS gripper, as shown in Figure 13, enabling measurement of contact force during grasping and harvesting. The measurement from the sensor is captured by the microcontroller of the gripper, which in turn is sent as a ROS topic to the whole CARPOS system. let $f_c(t), \forall t \in [0, T]$ be this measurement during the kinesthetic demonstration of the harvesting skill.

For encoding $f_c(t)$, a Radial Base Function (RBF) network is utilized as a regressor, which encodes the time-series through the weighted sum of RBFs. Selecting the Gaussian RBFs, the utilized regressor has the following form:

$$\hat{f}_c(x) = \sum_{i=1}^L w_{f,i} \psi_i(x) = \mathbf{W}_f^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}(x), \quad (27)$$

Figure 13 – Force sensor in the thumb of the robotic gripper

where $\hat{f}_c \in \mathbb{R}$ is the encoded (regressed) force, $x \in \mathbb{R}$ is the phase variable of the DMP, $w_{f,i} \in \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, \dots, L$ are the weights that essentially encode the characteristics of the force time-series, $\psi_i(x)$, $i = 1, \dots, L$ are the Gaussian kernels provided in (3), $\mathbf{W}_f \triangleq [w_{f,1} \ w_{f,2} \ \dots \ w_{f,L}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^L$ is the vector of the weights and $\Psi(x) \triangleq [\psi_1(x) \ \dots \ \psi_L(x)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^L$ is the Gaussian Radial Base. i.e. the vector with the values of all the base functions, with $L \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of RBFs utilized, which is pre-defined.

For finding the weights that optimally encode the demonstrated force pattern, one has to solve the following optimization problem:

$$\mathbf{W}_f^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}_f} \int_0^T \mathbf{W}_f^T \Psi(x(t)) - f_c(t) \ dt, \quad (28)$$

which, given the discrete form of the time-series of $f_c(t)$, is solved using the Least-Squares formula, similarly to the one employed in (6) above.

An example of this RBF-based encoding is presented in Fig. 14 for an arbitrary selected signal. Notice the difference in accuracy achieved with 10 and 40 kernels respectively. However, let us highlight that a more accurate approximation, which is achieved by using more kernels, possibly will also encode the high-frequency noise of the demonstrated time-series, therefore there is trade-off between high accuracy and noise rejection, which can be achieved by selecting a moderate number of kernels.

Notice that the encoding of this contact force is done based on the phase variable of the DMP, in order for this value to be synchronized with the motion of the end-effector. This feature augments the original DMP in $SE(3)$ by one more dimension. In particular, in order to guide the motion of the robot towards achieving these learned forces, we propose the utilization of an additional term in the first equation of the position DMP, i.e. eq. (8), which proportionally moves the robot towards the direction of the contact force based on the contact force error. The complete “force-aware” DMP model, involving (8) and (10), is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau^2 \ddot{\mathbf{p}} &= a(b(\mathbf{p}_T - \mathbf{p}) - \tau \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + s \mathbf{f}_p(x; \mathbf{w}) + k_f \mathbf{n}_s(\hat{f}_c(x; \mathbf{W}_f) - f_c), \\ \tau \dot{\mathbf{z}} &= -a_z(b_z \mathbf{e}_Q + \mathbf{z}) + s_z \mathbf{f}_z(x; \mathbf{W}_o), \\ \tau \dot{\mathbf{e}}_Q &= \mathbf{z}, \\ \tau \dot{x} &= g(x),\end{aligned}\tag{29}$$

where $\mathbf{n}_s \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the unit vector of the contact force measurement direction (shown in Fig. 13) and $k_f \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ a pre-defined tunable gain for this force-control action.

Figure 14 – RBF-based encoding with 10 and 40 kernels.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Motion encoding

Multiple full training procedures are executed and recorded, utilizing the complete CARPOS robotic system, i.e. the UR10e robotic manipulator attached on a Clearpath Husky platform (depicted in Figure 15), with a RealSense camera attached to the robot's end-effector as depicted in Fig. 13. For enabling extensive testing of our methodologies horizontally within the CARPOS project, we designed and fabricated (using a 3D printer) an "artificial stem", emulating the detachment of the fruit from the branch, employing a combination of magnets, as depicted in Figure 16. This artificial stem emulates the real stem abruption which firstly requires a rotation, followed by a translation, as a single translation without any rotation would require significantly larger forces. The experimental setup involved a real tomato plant with the mockup tomato fruit, as depicted in Fig. 15. For demonstrating the encoding functionality and performance of the CARPOS framework, described above, the results of a representative full training procedure are provided. More specifically, in Figure 17, the paths after the data fusion in each of the following steps are depicted, with respect to the frame of the fruit (red area in the figure):

- **Step 1: First visual observation** (Fig. 15a).
 - o Sampling rate: **30 Hz** (due to the camera fps).
 - o The camera was observing the scene from its initial pose which was towards facing the x-z plane of the initial hand configuration.

- **Step 2: Data fusion based on the LAIF method**, using the data from the second corrected visual observation, from another point of view (Fig. 15b).
 - o Sampling rate: **30 Hz** (also due to the camera fps)
 - o The camera was firstly automatically raised above the scene, i.e. approximately facing the y-z plane of the initial hand's pose, **due to the action of the active perception of the LAIF method**.

- **Step 3: Fusion in the physical layer based on the kinesthetic inspection and correction phase** (Fig. 15c).
 - o Sampling rate: **500 Hz** (due to the robot's high proprioceptive sampling rate)
 - o The human was guided towards corrections based on the uncertainty from the visual observations, **utilizing the proposed method**.

Figure 15 – The three phases of the training procedure for encoding the skill

Figure 16 – The artificial stem emulating the detachment of the real fruit

Figure 17 – The paths of the training dataset at each one of the three training steps detailed above

From Figure 17a, one can clearly see that the significant difference of the data fusion of the two visual observations, as compared to the initial observation, is along the y-axis of the motion. This was expected, as the maximum uncertainty of the first observation was along the y-axis. Regarding the kinesthetic correction, it is visible from Fig. 17b, that during the interaction with the robot, the human realized that the pattern did not involve a significant translation along the z-axis and physically re-shaped the path, just after the first third of the motion, in order to also encode a translation for detaching the fruit (along the z axis of the fruit, see Fig. 15a for the axes). The lack of this translation for the detachment could possibly source from the wrongly terminated visual recording, i.e. the recording of the motion pattern was terminated before the end of the complete detachment motion, which however constitutes a realistic case. Notice that only two visual steps are considered, as after the second visual observation the uncertainty of the fused data was estimated significantly low, which means that another iteration would not significantly improve the quality of the data gathered.

In Figure 18, the encoding performance, using $N=20$ base functions, is shown for each one of these steps. Let us highlight that in these figures the motion is presented with respect to the initial hand pose, as this is the reference coordinate frame for the encoding². The actual measurements of the training dataset are depicted in dashed line, while the encoded by the DMP motion is depicted with solid line. Notice how the DMP smoothly encodes the visual data, even though the low sampling rate of the visual demonstrations (Fig. 18a and b) and the fact that the hand-perception algorithm was not able to perceive the human hand from $t \approx 0.8s$ to $t \approx 1.6$ (between the red dashed lines in Fig. 18a). Further, notice that after the second visual iteration, the significant change appears only along the y-axis of the demonstrated motion, as the fusion accounts for the

² This is why the motion starts from $p(0) = [0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$, $Q(0) = [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$.

uncertainty of the previous demonstration, which was maximum along the y-axis (due to considering a larger uncertainty along the depth axis of the camera). Lastly, notice the data quality of the kinesthetic correction, due to the high sampling rate of the proprioceptive sensors of the robot (500Hz) and their high accuracy, which helps the DMP to achieve an encoding with significantly improved quality. The Root Mean Square approximation errors are provided in Table I both in position and orientation. Notice how the approximation through the DMP is gradually improved, which demonstrates that each one of the considered training steps make the accumulated data more “encodable”.

Figure 18– The encoding performance at each consecutive phase of the training procedure. Red arrows signify significant changes of the pattern. Dashed line: the training dataset (fused in each step), solid line: the smooth encoding by the DMP.

Table I – The RMS of the approximation errors in each step of the training procedure

Step	RMS of position approximation error [mm]	RMS of orientation approximation error [degrees]
First vis. observation	19.59	9.32
Fusion of the two vis. observations	16.69	4.85
Fused after the kinesthetic corrections	0.26	0.14

Generalization to different poses and fruit sizes

For demonstrating the adaptability of the encoding mechanism to different positions, orientations and sizes of the fruit, two experiments were conducted, one using a relatively small plastic tomato (radius $\sim 3\text{cm}$) and one using a relatively larger one (radius $\sim 4\text{cm}$), both of which were located in different positions and orientations; the mockup tomatoes utilized are shown in Figure 19.

$r=0.03\text{m}$ $r=0.04\text{m}$

Figure 19 - The two mockup tomatoes utilized

The resulted paths followed in each case are depicted in Figure 20. In Figure 20a the paths are translated, in order to start from the origin of the coordinate frames for comparing the spatial scaling of the motion done based on the size of the tomato, while in Figure 20b the paths are not translated (presented as actually executed) in order to demonstrate the generalization of the path for different positions and orientations of the fruit. Notice how the pattern is slightly scaled in order to account for the size of the tomato, while also generalizing both its position and orientation based on the pose variation of the tomato in each case.

a) The paths of the motion of the end-effector in the two cases, translated to the origin of the coordinate frame for comparison

b) The paths of the motion of the end-effector in the two cases

Figure 20 - The paths followed by the end-effector for the two different tomatoes.

Force encoding

For demonstrating the force encoding and force-based trajectory shaping functionalities of the proposed method, we provide the results from a representative example of a skill learned after the visual and kinesthetic means described above. In Figure 21, the actual measured force measured from the contact sensor attached to the fingertip of the gripper is shown after removing the initial bias, as well as the encoded pattern through the RBF regressor described above. Notice the pattern appearing during the detachment of the fruit, i.e. between the two red dashed lines. For the encoding only $N=10$ RBFs were utilized, in order to achieve significant noise rejection.

Figure 21- The encoding of the contact force applied by the finger of the gripper. Blue line: The actual measurements after removing the bias, orange line: The encoded pattern using the RBF regressor.

For shaping the trajectory in real-time during the autonomous execution, we utilize the DMP provided in (29) with a $k_f = 0.2$. For assessing the magnitude of the shaping achieved based on the proposed enhanced DMP model, we executed two experiments of autonomous fruit picking, one with considering the force-based shaping term in (29), and one without this term. In Figure 22, the two paths followed by the end-effector are depicted. Notice how the path is shaped based on the encoded forces and the actual ones, as the gripper is essentially pulling the tomato's stem in order to achieve the encoded force, and consequently detach the fruit as demonstrated (the axis of the contact force sensor is also depicted in Fig. 22). Further notice that when the detachment is completed, no further shaping of the motion is performed, as expected. Lastly, the calculated Mean Square Error (MSE) of the value $\| \hat{f}_c(x; \mathbf{W}_f) - f_c \|$ during the two cases are: 65.69 when the force-based shaping is enabled and 99.03 when this term is switched off, which shows that the executed force profile was slightly closer to the learned pattern, when the force-based shaping is employed. However, let us highlight that this error is not negligible even when utilizing the proposed term,

due to the fact that a relatively low $k_f = 0.2$ was utilized for safety reasons, as a high k_f could potentially result in relatively large and abrupt motions, in case of significant scene variations.

Figure 22 - The paths followed by the end-effector with and without the proposed force-based shaping enabled

[EXTRA RESEARCH INVESTIGATION] SEGMENTING A DEMONSTRATED MOTION INTO PRIMITIVE ACTIONS USING LLMs

The investigation provided here was not included in the initial proposal, i.e. it is presented as additional material, but constitutes the first step towards the extension of the methods developed in CARPOS project for encoding a motion pattern. The investigation and its results will be presented as a Late Breaking Results (LBR) poster at the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN 2025); the related poster, as well as the corresponding technical report are provided in the Appendix of this deliverable.

The complex motion required for detaching a fruit from the branch depends on the type of the plant. However, in most of the cases, this complex motion is composed by a sequence of simpler primitive actions. As we only account for the detachment of the fruit, these primitive actions are considered to be the following: Pull, Slide, Swing, Tilt, Twist, as presented in Fig. 23, with either one of the first two (Pull or Slide) always appearing at the end of the complex detachment motion, as they involve a displacement of the fruit from the branch.

Figure 23 – The considered primitive actions

To teach a fruit picking skill to a novice farmer, humans firstly utilize verbal communication, i.e. linguistic explanation. An example sentence provided by an experienced farmer to the novice one, to this aim, could be the following: "To detach the fruit, you firstly have to twist it and then pull it from the branch.". In most cases, the experienced farmer also provides an example of the fruit picking procedure, by demonstrating it in front of the learner.

Inspired by the intuition characterizing the human-to-human skill transfer, in this work we aim at investigating the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for segmenting a complex sequence of primitive actions, in the context of the fruit picking task. Our aim is to exploit these capabilities as a part of Learning by Demonstration (LbD) for a robotic system which will be capable to learn from humans through intuitive means.

Towards tackling the problem above, given a time series of the generalized velocity, i.e. $\mathbf{v}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^6, t \in [0, T]$, of a complex fruit-picking motion, with respect to the initial pose of the fruit, with $T \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the duration of motion, our aim is to test the effectiveness of an LLM to simultaneously classify and segment the motion into the aforementioned five predefined primitive actions, shown in Fig. 23.

Notice that the velocity of the end-effector is considered, instead of its pose, in order to facilitate the segmentation by rejecting bias. In other words, by selecting the velocity instead of the pose, each action maintains its characteristics even if it follows after a displacement that could possibly have occurred due to the sequential nature of the complex motion considered.

Considered comparison:

For classifying and segmenting the time series into primitive actions, a custom Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) was created, based on OpenAI's GPT-4-turbo model via the ChatGPT

Custom GPT framework³. A key aspect of the configuration was the emphasis on rule-based classification, where the identification and segmentation of motions were grounded in the predefined kinematic characteristics listed in Table II, focusing on the dominant directional patterns observed in the translational and angular velocity components.

Table II - Kinematic characteristics of primitive actions.

Primitive	Characteristic Behavior
Pull	Translation along x -axis, without significant rotation
Slide	Translation on the $y - z$ plane, without significant rotation
Swing	Translation along the y -axis and rotation around the z -axis
Tilt	Minimal translation z -axis and rotation around y -axis
Twist	No translation, but rotation around x -axis

Three fine-tuning (learning / explanation) approaches are considered for our case study. The first approach (Approach A) involves only linguistic explanation of the primitive actions. In particular, in this approach the GPT model is only provided with descriptions of the characteristics of the primitive actions with respect to the expected major axes of motion for each one of them; the characteristics defined in Table II. In the second approach (Approach B), a small dataset of representative example motions for each primitive action is provided to the GPT model without however providing any linguistic explanation regarding the characteristics of motion; namely five examples for each primitive action. Finally, Approach C combines both means of Approach A and B, i.e. both linguistic explanation and example datasets are provided to the GPT model.

In all three approaches, the model was primed to recognize the motion primitives by examining the temporal evolution of the velocity signals and recognizing changes consistent with the prevalent axes defined for each motion type. Segmentation indices were derived by recognizing the earliest significant change in either translational or angular velocity, depending on the defining characteristics of the motion. This ensured that each primitive began at the point where its characteristic movement pattern first emerged. The resulting sequence of motion primitives followed a strict chronological order, determined by their respective start indices.

In order to allow consistent visualization of velocity profiles and to improve readability of motion transitions, a Python helper function was also provided in the GPT configurations to compute the supremum (maximum absolute value) of the translational and angular velocity components; the script is publicly available⁴. This method was then used to normalize the values of all plots so that an equivalent visual scale is shown regardless of motion magnitude. These resulting plots helped to visually inspect the segmentation boundary validity, making it easier to assess the accuracy and coherence of the identified primitives.

In line with the recognition and segmentation rules described above, the custom GPT produced an easy readable, structured list of motion primitives with a start index and end index marking a segment border within the time series. An example output format for a complex sequence

³ <https://help.openai.com/en/articles/8554397-creating-a-gpt>

⁴ https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/VerbalDMPcorrections/blob/526440db1fe64ebccb89fe27721f18fc069b9526/motion_classification_segmentation_time_series.ipynb

consisting of three distinct motion primitives, would appear as follows: twist (Index 0–62), tilt (Index 63–112), pull (Index 113–170). This clear and consistent representation supported both interpretability and smooth integration with tasks such as evaluation and visualization.

Data acquisition and Pre-processing

In order to create a smooth and cooperative human-robot interaction and capture the realistic motion behavior, a task-space admittance control scheme was employed, providing the robot with homogeneous compliance characteristics. For comparison purposes, a push-button was attached to the handles of the end-effector of the CARPOS robot, serving as a tool for precisely recording the exact moment of motion transitions while capturing the complex motion sequences which was used only as ground-truth data for the evaluation. When pressed, it generates a timestamp that effectively marks key transitions. To further emulate a real fruit-picking setup, a mock-up fruit was placed in the robot's gripper, with the fruit being, at the start of each motion, anchored to a vertical stand that mimicked the presence of a fruit stem. The experimental setup used is depicted in Fig. 24.

Figure 24 – Image from the demonstration of the pull primitive

All experimental data employed in this work were organized into three datasets: training (provided to the model in Approaches B and C as examples), validation (used for assessing the performance of Approach C with feedback) and testing, each of which consisted of time-series motion recordings in the same format described above. The training dataset was made up of five demonstrations of each motion primitive separately, i.e. 25 time-series in total. As for the testing dataset, its purpose was to assess the model's performance in all the considered approaches. It was made up of complex motion sequences made up of a sequence of the considered primitive actions.

The experimental data captured the full $SE(3)$ pose in formation, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_a(t), \mathbf{Q}_a(t), \forall t \in [0, T]$, provided by the forward kinematics of the robot at 500Hz. However, one of the important aspects regarding the communication with most of the current GPT models, is the data size provided to the model, with most of the manufacturers imposing data limits or introducing additional costs. Therefore, to resolve the problem of the high sampling density of the initial time-series (i.e. 500

Hz), the data were interpolated using the Nadaraya Watson kernel regression method [18], [19], significantly reducing, in this way, the size of the dataset, using Gaussian kernels [20]. This non-parametric approach provides an estimate, i.e. $\hat{y}(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}$, of an arbitrary timeseries $y(t)$, at a given time instance t_0 , by computing a kernel-weighted average of observed values y_i corresponding to time instances t_i (i.e. $y_i \triangleq y(t_i)$), as defined by:

$$\hat{y}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^v K(t - t_i) y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^v K(t - t_i)} \quad (30)$$

where $K \triangleq \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$ is the Gaussian kernel, which assigns weights to each observation at t_i based on its proximity to t , with $\sigma^2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ reflecting its variance. For the interpolation, $v = 20$ kernels per second were considered. Following the interpolation, to thoroughly analyze the dynamic behavior of the system, both translational and angular velocity vectors, i.e. $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_a(t)$, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_a(t)$ respectively, have been obtained from the non-causal (centered) numerical differentiation of the position and orientation data respectively. The latter ensures numerical consistency and preserves accuracy across all regions, yielding a discrete approximation of the continuous velocity profile from the estimated derivatives [21].

To compute the angular velocity vector from the unit quaternion derivative the following formula is used:

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_a(t) = 2\mathbf{J}_Q^T(\mathbf{Q}_a) \dot{\mathbf{Q}}_a(t), \quad (31)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_Q(\mathbf{Q}_a) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 3}$ is the matrix mapping the angular velocities to unit quaternion rates, defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{J}_Q(\mathbf{Q}_a) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} -\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T \\ \eta \mathbf{I}_3 + \mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (32)$$

with $\mathbf{S}(\cdot): \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ denoting the skew-symmetric matrix of an \mathbb{R}^3 vector and $\eta \in \mathbb{R}$, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ representing the scalar and vector part of the unit quaternion respectively, i.e. $\mathbf{Q}_a \triangleq [\eta \ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T]^T$. More details about the algebra of unit quaternions and its use for describing the orientation of a frame can be found in [22].

Approach A: Explanation through language

In this approach, the custom GPT model was tasked with identifying and segmenting a series of complex motion sequences using only the kinematic characteristics defined in advance in the model configuration. Importantly, in this approach, the model was not provided with any examples, training data, or data retrieved from motion primitives. Instead, it relied entirely on language-based reasoning, using descriptive rules about each motion behavior (see Table II). The prompt was aimed at looking at velocity profiles for the purpose of classifying motion boundaries, order of occurrence, and segmentation indices.

Approach B: Providing example measurements

Unlike the language-based reasoning of Approach A, this method, introduces an intermediate stage of learning where the GPT is provided with representative motion examples, corresponding to the individual motion primitives: pull, swing, slide, tilt, twist. In this approach, the specified kinematic characteristics of each motion are not provided to the GPT. Instead, the model has to learn and understand these characteristics implicitly.

Approach C: Combining explanations with examples

Approach C integrates the language-based reasoning of Approach A with the example-based reasoning of the Approach B, aiming to leverage the strengths that emerge from the combination of these two approaches. In more details, the model here is provided with both the specific kinematic characteristics and the representative motion examples.

Conclusions and the importance of providing feedback to the system

Building upon these findings, the need to provide feedback to the system is evident. The performance variations observed among the three approaches mentioned before indicate the potential for improvement through a targeted feedback process. Towards this direction, five out of the 20 complex motion sequences were used as a “validation” dataset for supplying corrective feedback to the system. **The results are detailed in there LBR report provided in the Appendix of the deliverable.** In the context of this experiment, the feedback approach provides some performance improvement by allowing the system to adjust its internal representations and decision processes based on indicated past mistakes and inconsistencies.

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APPENDIX A

LATE BREAKING RESULTS **POSTER** AND **REPORT** AT IEEE RO-MAN 2025

On the capabilities of LLMs for classifying and segmenting time series of fruit picking motions into primitive actions

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Nikolaos Efstathopoulos and Dimitrios Papageorgiou

2025
Eindhoven
IEEE RO-MAN

CARPOS
Coachable Robot
for Fruit Picking Operations

**Hellenic
Mediterranean
University**

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Motivation & Inspiration

To teach a fruit picking skill to a novice farmer, an experienced farmer firstly utilizes verbal communication, i.e. **linguistic explanation**.

Example sentence:

*"To detach the fruit, you firstly have to **twist it** and then **pull it** from the branch."*

In most of the cases, the experienced farmer also provides an example of the fruit picking procedure, by demonstrating it in front of the learner.

Research question:

Can we use LLMs to equip the robot with such skill learning capabilities?

Considered primitive actions, involved in fruit picking/detachment

Testing the hypothesis

Three fine-tuning cases are tested:

A) Explanation of the characteristics of the primitive actions only **through language**

B) Providing **example motion-timeseries** of the primitive actions ($SE(3)$ velocities)

C) Combination of the above

EXTRA - Providing feedback during the training

Data collection

Results:

- Identification of the sequence of primitive actions of **20 complex motion sequences**

Seq. No	1st Segment	2nd Segment	3rd Segment	4th Segment
1 *	tilt ●	slide ●	-	-
2	tilt ●	pull ●	-	-
3	swing X	slide ●	-	-
4	swing X	pull ●	-	-
5 *	twist ●	pull ●	-	-
6	twist ●	slide ●	-	-
7	twist ●	tilt X	slide X	-
8	swing ●	tilt ●	slide ●	-
9	swing ●	tilt ●	pull ●	-
10 *	twist ●	tilt ●	pull ●	-
11	tilt X	twist ●	slide X	-
12	tilt ●	twist ●	pull ●	-
13	swing ●	swing ●	slide X	-
14 *	swing ●	twist ●	pull ●	-
15	tilt ●	swing ●	slide X	-
16 *	tilt ●	swing ●	pull ●	-
17	twist ●	swing X	slide X	-
18	twist ●	swing ●	pull ●	-
19	twist ●	tilt ●	swing ●	pull ●
20	swing ●	tilt ●	twist ●	slide X

● Approach A: 11 / 56 (19%), ● Approach B: 8 / 56 (14%),
● Approach C: 16 / 56 (28%), ● Feedback Approach: 19 / 43 (44%),
X None, * Sequences in which feedback was provided

Providing feedback significantly improves the training

On the capabilities of LLMs for classifying and segmenting time series of fruit picking motions into primitive actions

Eleni Konstantinidou¹, Nikolaos Kounalakis², Nikolaos Efstathopoulos¹ and Dimitrios Papageorgiou^{1,3}

Abstract— Despite their recent introduction to human society, Large Language Models (LLMs) have significantly affected the way we tackle mental challenges in our everyday lives. From optimizing our linguistic communication to assisting us in making important decisions, LLMs, such as ChatGPT, are notably reducing our cognitive load by gradually taking on an increasing share of our mental activities. In the context of Learning by Demonstration (LbD), classifying and segmenting complex motions into primitive actions, such as pushing, pulling, twisting etc, is considered to be a key-step towards encoding a task. In this work, we investigate the capabilities of LLMs to undertake this task, considering a finite set of predefined primitive actions found in fruit picking operations. By utilizing LLMs instead of simple supervised learning or analytic methods, we aim at making the method easily applicable and deployable in a real-life scenario. Three different fine-tuning approaches are investigated, compared on datasets captured kinesthetically, using a UR10e robot, during a fruit-picking scenario.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a powerful force that is revolutionizing various fields by developing systems that mimic human intelligence, encompassing this way areas like reasoning, learning and problem-solving [1]. This transformation is primarily due to Large Language Models (LLMs), deep learning models capable of processing and generating natural language data and other content [2]. The evolution of LLMs was driven by the growth of the internet and increasing computing power, which fuelled the vision of Natural Language Processing (NLP) [3] through deep learning methods such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [4], and the Transformer model [5]. This nourished models like BERT [6] and Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT) [7], revolutionizing fields like text generation and language translation.

From a "robotics" perspective, segmenting a complex motion into primitive actions is a crucial step in learning human kinematic behaviors through demonstrations. While many works employ Deep Neural Networks (DNN) [8][9] for segmentation, and others propose analytic solutions [10][11]

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or even AI methods like Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN) [12] [13] for explicitly segmenting motion time-series, analytic methods require solid technical skills for action detection and classification, making them hard to deploy in a real-world scenario.

This work investigates LLM capabilities for classifying primitive actions and segmenting complex fruit-picking motions. In particular, we explore and compare three LLM fine-tuning approaches: a) using only linguistic explanation of the primitive action, b) using a small dataset of representative example motions (e.g., five samples per action) and c) combining both a) and b) approaches. The utilized datasets for both the fine-tuning and experimental evaluation/comparison of the approaches, consists of kinesthetically captured data, i.e. motion time-series captured by having the human demonstrating the motion directly by moving the robot's end-effector through physical contact.

II. MOTIVATION AND PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The advantages of picking a fruit without utilizing cutting tools span from ensuring the safety of the plant and fruit, to being effective, as in many cases there are no cutting affordances for the insertion of a cutting tool (e.g. in the case of peaches). The complex motion required for detaching a fruit from the branch depends on the type of the plant. However, in most of the cases, this complex motion is composed by a sequence of simpler primitive actions. As we only account for the detachment of the fruit, these primitive actions are considered to be the following: *Pull*, *Slide*, *Swing*, *Tilt*, *Twist*, as presented in Fig. 1, with either one of the first two (*Pull* or *Slide*) always appearing at the end of the complex detachment motion, as they involve a displacement of the fruit from the branch.

Fig. 1: The considered primitive actions

To teach a fruit picking skill to a novice farmer, humans firstly utilize verbal communication, i.e. linguistic explanation. An example sentence provided by an experienced farmer to the novice one, to this aim, could be the following: "To detach the fruit, you firstly have to twist it and then pull it from the branch.". In most of the cases, the experienced farmer also provides an example of the fruit

picking procedure, by demonstrating it in front of the learner. Inspired by the intuition characterizing the human-to-human skill transfer, in this work we aim at investigating the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for segmenting a complex sequence of primitive actions, in the context of the fruit picking task. Our aim is to exploit these capabilities as a part of Learning by Demonstration (LbD) for a robotic system which will be capable to learn from humans through intuitive means.

Let us assume the availability of a demonstrated fruit picking motion. Therefore, let $\{F\}$ be the frame at the initial fruit’s pose and $\mathbf{x}(t) \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^\top(t) \ \mathbf{Q}^\top(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ be the pose of the robot’s end-effector with respect to $\{F\}$, where $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbf{Q}(t) \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are the end-effector’s position and orientation in unit quaternion form respectively, with \mathbb{S}^3 denoting the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^4 . Moreover, let $\mathbf{v}(t) \triangleq [\dot{\mathbf{p}}^\top(t) \ \boldsymbol{\omega}^\top(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6$ be the generalized velocity of the end-effector with respect to $\{F\}$, with $\dot{\mathbf{p}}(t), \boldsymbol{\omega}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being its linear and angular velocity respectively. Given that $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is provided by the forward kinematics of the robot, one can calculate a numerical approximate of $\mathbf{v}(t)$, based on the numerical differentiation of the pose, as described in the following section.

Given a time series of the generalized velocity, $\mathbf{v}(t), t \in [0, T]$, of a complex fruit-picking motion, with respect to the initial pose of the fruit, with $T \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the duration of motion, our aim is to test the effectiveness of an LLM to simultaneously classify and segment the motion into the aforementioned five predefined primitive actions, shown in Fig. 1.

Notice that the velocity of the end-effector is considered, instead of its pose, in order to facilitate the segmentation by rejecting bias. In other words, by selecting the velocity instead of the pose, each action maintains its characteristics even if it follows after a displacement that could possibly have occurred due to the sequential nature of the complex motion considered.

III. CONSIDERED APPROACHES AND COMPARISON

For classifying and segmenting the time series into primitive actions, a custom Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) was created, based on OpenAI’s GPT-4-turbo model via the ChatGPT Custom GPT framework¹. A key aspect of the configuration was the emphasis on rule-based classification, where the identification and segmentation of motions were grounded in the predefined kinematic characteristics listed in Table I, focusing on the dominant directional patterns observed in the translational and angular velocity components.

Three fine-tuning (learning / explanation) approaches are considered for our case study. The first approach (Approach A) involves only linguistic explanation of the primitive actions. In particular, in this approach the GPT model is

only provided with descriptions of the characteristics of the primitive actions with respect to the expected major axes of motion for each one of them; the characteristics defined in Table I. In the second approach (Approach B), a small dataset of representative example motions for each primitive action is provided to the GPT model without however providing any linguistic explanation regarding the characteristics of motion; namely five examples for each primitive action. Finally, Approach C combines both means of Approach A and B, i.e. both linguistic explanation and example datasets are provided to the GPT model.

TABLE I: Kinematic characteristics of primitive actions.

Primitive	Characteristic Behavior
<i>Pull</i>	Translation along x -axis, without significant rotation
<i>Slide</i>	Translation on the $y - z$ plane, without significant rotation
<i>Swing</i>	Translation along the y -axis and rotation around the z -axis
<i>Tilt</i>	Minimal translation z -axis and rotation around y -axis
<i>Twist</i>	No translation, but rotation around x -axis

In all three approaches, the model was primed to recognize the motion primitives by examining the temporal evolution of the velocity signals and recognizing changes consistent with the prevalent axes defined for each motion type. Segmentation indices were derived by recognizing the earliest significant change in either translational or angular velocity, depending on the defining characteristics of the motion. This ensured that each primitive began at the point where its characteristic movement pattern first emerged. The resulting sequence of motion primitives followed a strict chronological order, determined by their respective start indices.

In order to allow consistent visualization of velocity profiles and to improve readability of motion transitions, a Python helper function was also provided in the GPT configurations to compute the supremum (maximum absolute value) of the translational and angular velocity components; the script is publicly available². This method was then used to normalize the values of all plots so that an equivalent visual scale is shown regardless of motion magnitude. These resulting plots helped to visually inspect the segmentation boundary validity, making it easier to assess the accuracy and coherence of the identified primitives.

In line with the recognition and segmentation rules described above, the custom GPT produced an easy readable, structured list of motion primitives with a start index and end index marking a segment border within the time series. An example output format for a complex sequence consisting of three distinct motion primitives, would appear as follows: *twist (Index 0–62)*, *tilt (Index 63–112)*, *pull (Index 113–170)*. This clear and consistent representation supported both interpretability and smooth integration with tasks such as evaluation and visualization.

¹<https://help.openai.com/en/articles/8554397-creating-a-gpt>

²GitHub link to script

A. Data Acquisition and Pre-processing

In order to create a smooth and cooperative human-robot interaction and capture the realistic motion behavior, a task-space admittance control scheme was employed, providing the robot with homogeneous compliance characteristics. For comparison purposes, a push-button was attached to the handles of the end-effector of the UR10e, serving as a tool for precisely recording the exact moment of motion transitions while capturing the complex motion sequences which was used only as ground-truth data for the evaluation. When pressed, it generates a timestamp that effectively marks key transitions. To further emulate a real fruit-picking setup, a mock-up fruit was placed in the robot’s gripper, with the fruit being, at the start of each motion, anchored to a vertical stand that mimicked the presence of a fruit stem. The experimental setup used is depicted in Fig.2.

Fig. 2: Image from the demonstration of the *pull* primitive.

All experimental data employed in this work were organized into three datasets: training (provided to the model in Approaches B and C as examples), validation (used for assessing the performance of Approach C with feedback) and testing, each of which consisted of time-series motion recordings in the same format described above. The training dataset was made up of five demonstrations of each motion primitive separately, i.e. 25 time-series in total. As for the testing dataset, its purpose was to assess the model’s performance in all the considered approaches. It was made up of complex motion sequences made up of a sequence of the considered primitive actions.

B. Pre-processing

The experimental data captured the full $SE(3)$ pose information, i.e. $\mathbf{x}(t), \forall t \in [0, T]$, provided by the forward kinematics of the robot at 500Hz. However, one of the important aspects regarding the communication with most of the current GPT models, is the data size provided to the model, with most of the manufacturers imposing data limits or introducing additional costs. Therefore, to resolve the problem of the high sampling density of the initial time-series (i.e. 500 Hz), the data were interpolated using the Nadaraya-Watson kernel regression method [14], [15], significantly reducing, in this way, the size of the dataset, using Gaussian kernels [16]. This non-parametric approach provides an estimate, i.e. $\hat{y}(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}$, of an arbitrary timeseries $y(t)$, at a given time instance t_0 , by computing a kernel-weighted average of observed values y_i corresponding to time instances t_i (i.e.

$y_i \triangleq y(t_i)$), as defined by:

$$\hat{y}(t) \triangleq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n K(t - t_i) y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n K(t - t_i)}, \quad (1)$$

where $K(t) \triangleq \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the Gaussian kernel, which assigns weights to each observation at t_i based on its proximity to t , with $\sigma^2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ reflecting its variance. For the interpolation, 20 kernels per second were considered. Following the interpolation, to thoroughly analyze the dynamic behavior of the system, both translational and angular velocity vectors, i.e. $\dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ respectively, have been obtained from the non-causal (centered) numerical differentiation of the position and orientation data respectively. The latter ensures numerical consistency and preserves accuracy across all regions, yielding a discrete approximation of the continuous velocity profile from the estimated derivatives [17].

To compute the angular velocity vector from the unit quaternion derivative the following formula is used:

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) = 2\mathbf{J}_Q^T(\mathbf{Q})\dot{\mathbf{Q}}(t), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_Q(\mathbf{Q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 3}$ is the matrix mapping the angular velocities to unit quaternion rates, defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{J}_Q(\mathbf{Q}) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} -\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T \\ \eta \mathbf{I}_3 + \mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{S}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ denoting the skew-symmetric matrix of an \mathbb{R}^3 vector and $\eta \in \mathbb{R}, \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ representing the scalar and vector part of the unit quaternion respectively, i.e. $\mathbf{Q} \triangleq [\eta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T]^T$. More details about the algebra of unit quaternions and its use for describing the orientation of a frame can be found in [18].

C. Approach A: Explanation through language

In this approach, the custom GPT model was tasked with identifying and segmenting a series of complex motion sequences using only the kinematic characteristics defined in advance in the model configuration. Importantly, in this approach, the model was not provided with any examples, training data, or data retrieved from motion primitives. Instead, is relied entirely on language-based reasoning, using descriptive rules about each motion behavior (see Table I). The prompt was aimed at looking at velocity profiles for the purpose of classifying motion boundaries, order of occurrence, and segmentation indices.

D. Approach B: Providing example measurements

Unlike the language-based reasoning of Approach A, this method, introduces an intermediate stage of learning where the GPT is provided with representative motion examples, corresponding to the individual motion primitives: *pull*, *swing*, *slide*, *tilt*, *twist*. In this approach, the specified kinematic characteristics of each motion are not provided to the GPT. Instead, the model has to learn and understand these characteristics implicitly.

(a) Approaches A, B and C (b) With and without feedback

Fig. 3: Statistical comparison of segmentation error across four approaches.

E. Approach C: Combining explanations with examples

Approach C integrates the language-based reasoning of Approach A with the example-based reasoning of the Approach B, aiming to leverage the strengths that emerge from the combination of these two approaches. In more details, the model here is provided with both the specific kinematic characteristics and the representative motion examples.

The performance of the approaches in 20 different complex motion sequences (involving 56 primitive actions) are provided in Table II and Fig. 3 for the classification and segmentation respectively. Notice that all 20 sequences are considered as the testing dataset for Approaches A, B and C, without the requirement of a “validation” dataset.

TABLE II: Classification of the 20 complex motion sequences, namely 5 validation sequences for the feedback approach and 15 as the testing dataset.

Seq. No	1st Segment	2nd Segment	3rd Segment	4th Segment
1 *	tilt ●	slide ●	–	–
2	tilt ●	pull ●	–	–
3	swing ✗	slide ●	–	–
4	swing ✗	pull ●	–	–
5 *	twist ●	pull ●	–	–
6	twist ●	slide ●	–	–
7	twist ●	tilt ✗	slide ✗	–
8	swing ●	tilt ●	slide ●	–
9	swing ●	tilt ●	pull ●	–
10 *	twist ●	tilt ●	pull ●	–
11	tilt ✗	twist ●	slide ✗	–
12	tilt ●	twist ●	pull ●	–
13	swing ●	swing ●	slide ✗	–
14 *	swing ●	twist ●	pull ●	–
15	tilt ●	swing ●	slide ✗	–
16 *	tilt ●	swing ●	pull ●	–
17	twist ●	swing ✗	slide ✗	–
18	twist ✗	swing ●	pull ●	–
19	twist ●	tilt ●	swing ●	pull ●
20	swing ●	tilt ●	twist ●	slide ✗

● Approach A: 11 / 56 (19%), ● Approach B: 8 / 56 (14%),
 ● Approach C: 16 / 56 (28%), ● Feedback Approach: 19 / 43 (44%),
 ✗ None, * Sequences in which feedback was provided

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE SYSTEM

Building upon these findings, the need to provide feedback to the system is evident. The performance variations observed among the three approaches mentioned before indicate the

potential for improvement through a targeted feedback process. Towards this direction, five out of the 20 complex motion sequences were used as a “validation” dataset for supplying corrective feedback to the system. The results are also shown in Table II and Fig. 3. In the context of this experiment, the feedback approach provides some performance improvement by allowing the system to adjust its internal representations and decision processes based on indicated past mistakes and inconsistencies.

Our next research steps are to increase the performance of the system and apply such methods for providing an intuitive LLM-based human-robot interface for scaling only parts of the learned motion sequence.

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